

Wearable Reader for Visual impairment People with vibrational feedback

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KEYWORDS

Raspberry Pi, Assistive Technology, Visually Impaired, Optical Character Recognition (OCR), Text-to-Speech (TTS), Wearable Device.

ABSTRACT

The Raspberry Pi Based Wearable Reader for Visually Impaired People with Haptic Feedback is an assistive system designed to help visually impaired individuals read printed text independently. The system uses a camera to capture text, Optical Character Recognition (OCR) to extract it, and a Text-to-Speech (TTS) engine to convert it into audio output. Additionally, vibration motors provide haptic feedback to guide users and indicate system status. The device is portable, cost-effective, and suitable for real-time usage. This system enhances accessibility, independence, and usability for visually impaired individuals[1][2].

I. INTRODUCTION

Visual impairment significantly affects a person’s ability to access printed information such as books, newspapers, and sign boards. Traditional assistive methods like Braille and screen readers have limitations, as Braille is not universally available and screen readers are restricted to digital content. Recent advancements in embedded systems and computer vision have enabled the development of portable assistive devices that can interpret printed text in real time.

The Raspberry Pi has emerged as powerful and affordable platform for such applications due to its flexibility and ability to interface with cameras and sensors. Researchers have previously developed

OCR-based systems that convert printed text into speech for visually impaired users [1]. However, many of these systems lack portability and multi-sensory feedback. The proposed system addresses these limitations by integrating OCR, TTS, and haptic feedback into a wearable, device, thereby enhancing usability and independence [2][3].

The rapid advancement in embedded systems, computer vision, and artificial intelligence, new opportunities have merged to develop more efficient assistive technologies. The Raspberry Pi, a compact and affordable signal-board computer, provides an ideal perform for building such systems due to its ability to interface with cameras, sensors, and various peripherals. This project proposes a

wearable reading device that utilizes Raspberry Pi to capture printed text, process it using OCR, and convert it into speech using TTS technology. Furthermore, the integration of haptic feedback enhances user interaction by providing vibration-based signals, making the system more effective even in noisy environment.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

The development of assistive technologies for visually impaired individuals has gained significant attention in recent years, especially with advancements in computer vision, embedded systems, and artificial intelligence. One of the most widely used approaches in assistive reading devices is Optical Character Recognition (OCR), which enables the extraction of text from images. According to Ray Smith [4], OCR systems such as Tesseract have demonstrated high accuracy in recognizing printed text and have been widely adopted in various applications, including assistive devices for the visually impaired. These systems form the backbone of modern text-reading technologies.

Several researchers have proposed systems that combine OCR with Text-to-Speech (TTS) technology to assist visually impaired users. Kaur and Kaur [1] developed a text recognition system that captures printed text using a camera and converts it into speech output. Their study highlighted that OCR combined with TTS can significantly improve accessibility by enabling users to access printed information independently. However, their system was primarily limited to basic text recognition and lacked portability and real-time performance.

With the emergence of embedded platforms, researchers have increasingly adopted devices like Raspberry Pi for assistive applications due to their low cost, compact size, and flexibility. Sharma et al. [2] proposed a Raspberry Pi-based assistive system that integrates a camera module and OCR software to read printed text. Their system demonstrated that Raspberry Pi is capable for handling image processing and speech synthesis tasks efficiently. However, the system mainly relied on audio output, which may not be effective in noisy environments or situations where users require silent feedback.

The proposed system builds upon these research efforts by integrating OCR, TTS, and haptic feedback into a single wearable device using Raspberry Pi. By

combining these technologies, the system aims to overcome the limitations of existing solutions and provide a cost-effective, portable, and user-friendly assistive device that enhances independence for visually impaired individuals.

3. EXISTING METHOD

The existing system for assisting visually impaired individuals using a Raspberry Pi is primarily based on image processing and audio output technologies. In these systems, a camera module captures an image of the printed text, which is then processed using Optical Character Recognition (OCR) software such as Tesseract OCR engine to extract the textual content. The extracted text is subsequently converted into speech using Text-to-Speech (TTS) engines like eSpeak TTS engine, allowing the user to listen to the content through headphones or speakers. Most existing solutions rely on the Raspberry Pi 4 Model B as the central processing unit due to its affordability and capability to handle image processing tasks. However, these systems are often limited in functionality, as they mainly provide audio output without additional feedback mechanisms such as haptic alerts. Furthermore, many of them are either stationary or only partially portable, requiring the user to manually position the camera, and they may suffer from reduced accuracy under poor lighting conditions or with complex fonts. Processing delays and lack of real-time interaction also affect their efficiency. Hence, while existing systems provide a basic and cost-effective solution for text reading, they still lack advanced features like wearable convenience, fast processing, and multi-sensory feedback.

4. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed system is designed as a wearable assistive device that helps visually impaired individuals read printed text using image processing, speech synthesis, and haptic feedback. The system uses a Raspberry Pi as the main processing unit, which is connected to a camera module for capturing images of printed text. When the user activates the device, the camera captures an image, which is then processed using Optical Character Recognition (OCR) to extract textual information. OCR plays a vital role in converting image-based text into a digital format and has been widely used in assistive technologies for visually impaired users [1][4].

After extracting the text, the system converts it into speech using Text-to-Speech (TTS) engine. The generated audio is delivered through a speaker or headphones, allowing the user to listen to the content easily. Studies have shown that combining OCR and TTS provides an effective solution for accessing printed materials independently[1][2].

To enhance user interaction, the system also incorporates haptic feedback using vibration motors. These motors provide simple tactile signals to indicate system status, such as successful image capture or errors. This feature is particularly useful in noisy environments where audio feedback alone may not be sufficient [3].

The entire system is designed to be portable and wearable, enabling hands-free operation. It runs on a Python-based environment using the Raspbian operating system and is capable of real-time processing without requiring internet connectivity. By integrating OCR, TTS and haptic feedback into a single device, the system provides a cost-effective and user-friendly solution that improves accessibility and independence for visually impaired individuals.

5. WORKING PRINCIPLE

The working principle of a Raspberry Pi-based wearable reader for visually impaired people is based on capturing printed text, processing it, and converting it into audio output. Initially, the user activates the device using a button or voice command, which triggers the camera module to capture an image of the text. This image is then sent to the processing unit, typically the Raspberry Pi 4 Model B, where it undergoes image preprocessing to improve clarity. The processed image is passed to an Optical Character Recognition (OCR) system such as the Tesseract OCR engine, which extracts the textual information from the image. Once the text is obtained, it is forwarded to a Text-to-Speech (TTS) engine like eSpeak TTS engine, which converts the text into spoken words. The audio output is then delivered to the user through earphones or a speaker, enabling them to understand the content. In systems with haptic feedback, a vibration motor is also activated to provide tactile signals, such as confirming that the text has been successfully captured or alerting the user during operation. This integrated process allows visually

impaired users to access printed information independently in a simple and efficient manner.

BLOCK DIAGRAM

Fig. 4.1. Block Diagram

6. RESULTS AND OUTCOMES

The proposed Raspberry Pi-based wearable reader system was successfully designed and implemented to assist visually impaired individuals in reading printed text. The system was able to capture images using the camera module and accurately extract textual information using Optical Character Recognition (OCR). The extracted text was then converted into speech using a Text-to-Speech (TTS) engine, providing clear and understandable audio output to the user. The performance of OCR and TTS integration in assistive systems has been proven effective in similar studies [1][2].

Fig. 5.1. Output 1

Fig. 5.2. Output 2

The system demonstrated reliable real-time performance under normal lighting conditions, with acceptable accuracy in recognizing printed text from books, labels, and signboards. The addition of haptic feedback through vibration motors provided useful tactile signals, helping users understand system status such as successful image capture or errors. This multi-sensory approach improved usability, especially in environments where audio feedback alone was not sufficient, as supported by previous research [3].

The system consists of hardware and software components working together to provide a seamless experience. The hardware includes a Raspberry Pi, camera module, speaker, vibration motor, and power supply. The Raspberry Pi processes the captured images using OCR software such as Tesseract and converts the extracted text into speech using TTS engines. The software is implemented using Python on the Raspbian operating system. Previous research has demonstrated that embedded systems like Raspberry Pi can efficiently handle image processing and speech synthesis tasks for assistive applications [2]. The integration of these technologies ensures real-time performance and reliability.

The device was found to be portable, user-friendly and cost-effective, making it suitable for everyday use. It operates without requiring internet connectivity, which increases its reliability in different environments. Overall, the system achieved its objective of enhancing accessibility and independence for visually impaired individuals by providing an efficient and practical assistive solution.

7. CONCLUSION

The Raspberry Pi based wearable reader with haptic feedback presents an effective and innovative solution for assisting visually impaired individuals in accessing printed information independently. The system successfully integrates Optical Character Recognition (OCR), Text-to-Speech (TTS), and haptic feedback technologies into a single compact device. The experimental results show that the system can accurately capture printed text, process it efficiently, and convert it into clear audio output in real time. This enables users to read books, labels, and signboards without external assistance. Similar assistive systems based on OCR and TTS have demonstrated significant improvements in accessibility and user independence [1][2].

Furthermore, the inclusion of haptic feedback enhances the usability of the system by providing additional tactile cues that indicate system status, such as successful image capture or processing errors. This feature is particularly beneficial in noisy environments where audio feedback alone may not be sufficient, as supported by earlier research on multi-sensory assistive technologies [3]. The wearable design of the device ensures portability and allows hands-free operation, making it suitable for everyday use.

In addition to its functionality, the system is designed to be cost-effective and energy-efficient, which makes it accessible to a larger population. The ability to operate without internet connectivity further increases its reliability in different real-world conditions. Overall, the proposed system meets its primary objective of improving accessibility and enhancing the independence of visually impaired individuals.

The project also provides a strong foundation for future advancements. Features such as multilingual text recognition, real-time continuous reading, artificial intelligence-based object detection, and integration with mobile applications can further enhance the system's capabilities. With these improvements, the device can evolve into a more comprehensive assistive solution that supports navigation and environmental awareness, thereby significantly improving the quality of life for visually impaired users.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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